

SERVICE TO THE COUNTRY IS THE DUTY OF EVERY CITIZEN

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Annotation: *This article describes the role of young people in the performance of their duties to the motherland, the level of patriotic spirit in young people, and provides detailed information about today's military service and the responsibilities of citizens.*

Key words: *Patriotism, motherland, homeland, military service, defense power.*

Developing period of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, the respect, preservation and reproduction of the traditions of war and labor should remain a key issue for the younger generation preparing for the defense of their homeland, and at the same time for those who perform this honorable task.

Preserving and promoting our traditions and national values is closely linked with the notion of this Homeland, the observance of a sacred duty such as loving and protecting the Homeland.

The term homeland is actually an Arabic word meaning motherland. The concept of homeland is used both broadly and narrowly. It is a broad concept if we consider the area where the representatives of one nation live together, where their ancestors have lived since ancient times. When a person is born and raised in a house, a neighborhood, a village, it is a narrow concept. No matter what we use the concept of Motherland, we must preserve, preserve and try to pass on to future generations the traditions and values that we have inherited from our ancestors.

Along with pursuing a policy of peace, the Republic of Uzbekistan is committed to ensuring the security, peace and stability of its citizens. In accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, it exercises the inalienable right to defense, and at the level of mental adequacy, the state provides military and defense capabilities.

Preparing young people for service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a national task. In order to solve this problem, pre-service basic training, including civil defense training, is a compulsory subject in the curriculum. Article 13 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On General Military Obligation and Military Service" stipulates that pre-service teachers in pre-service institutions must undergo courses or classes on the eve of graduation. Given the importance of this issue, the

direction of "Pre-conscription military education" in higher education, that is, one of the main disciplines in the training of future teachers "Pre-conscription training" is "Military-Pre-Conscription". patriotic education ”.

Youth is the future of our Motherland, our nation. As we entrust the destiny of our country to them, first of all, they must deeply understand the complex and responsible task entrusted to them and contribute to it. After all, love for the Motherland, love for it is directly determined by the creative work of everyone for the development of this country.

The upbringing of deep-thinking young people, imbued with the ideas of national patriotism, is of great importance in the development of national identity. Therefore, each of our young people preparing for the defense of the Motherland must be brought up in the spirit of high patriotism. Patriotism is a high human quality. Patriotism is one of the brightest aspects of perfection. That's it Hadith for both In Sharif « Motherland To love is to believe is done .

However, in the past world to civilization huge contribution added of the people today generations, own heritage world peoples by confession mature emphasizing transition it is permissible, because they have it this Feelings like _ national proud and mental perfection leads, national identity to understand aspiration strengthens .

Military patriotism upbringing physical education with personal depends on in the picture take only when good the result gives. That's it for military patriotism upbringing physical uneducated imagination so will not happen . In the cold and heat durable to be, to diseases quickly not giving up, difficulties overcoming, willpower . sabot - perseverance, fast and agile movement can do know such as Homeland to the defender specific qualities student - youth and in teachers in development physical education and soort games role indefinitely is large.

Young people patriotism in the spirit bring them up Homeland in defense physically and spiritual in terms of preparation necessity current of the day current functions is one .

General education study in institutions, secondary special and medium profession education in institutions students, this including higher education in schools education receiving student youth military patriotism in the spirit preparation now education work all systems through instead being increased .

Indeed, to the Homeland relatively really loyalty uni protection able to do to be Demand reaches Students military patriotism in the spirit upbringing all kind of activity showing education institutions basic place occupy.